

MATRITSA VA DETERMINANTLAR. ARALASHMANI TAYYORLASHDA KETGAN MODDALAR SARFINI TOPISH MASALASI

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doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11242685

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada matritsa va determinantlar hisobi hamda ularning analitik va matritsa usullarida bajarilgan hisoblari keltirilgan. Shuningdek aralashmani tayyorlashda ketgan moddalar sarfini topish masalasi zamonaviy kompyuter texnologiyalaridan foydalanib bajarish matritsalar usulida qulay ekanligi katilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: statik noaniq ramalar, kuchlar usuli, kanonik tenglamalar sistemasi, matritsalar usuli, determinant.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлено исчисление матриц и определителей и их расчеты аналитическими и матричными методами. Также показано, что расход веществ, используемых при приготовлении смеси, удобно находить с помощью современных компьютерных технологий матричным методом.

Ключевые слова: статические неопределенные системы координат, метод сил, система канонических уравнений, метод матриц, определитель.

Abstract. This article presents the calculus of matrices and determinants and their calculations by analytical and matrix methods. Also, it is shown that it is convenient to find the consumption of substances used in the preparation of the mixture using modern computer technologies using the matrix method.

Key words: static uncertain frames, method of forces, system of canonical equations, method of matrices, determinant.

Matritsa haqida tushuncha.

Ushbu ko'rinishdagi sonlardan tuzilgan:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

jadvallarga matritsalar, a_{11}, a_{12}, \dots lar ularning elementlari deyiladi.

Agar matritsada satrlar soni ustunlar soniga teng bo'lsa, u kvadrat matritsa deyiladi. Uning satrlar yoki ustunlar soniga tartibi deyiladi. Masalan, keltirilgan matritsalaridan 1-si 2-tartibli 3-si esa uchinchi tartibli matritsa. Agar matritsaning satrlar soni ustunlar soniga teng bo'lmasa, u to'g'ri burchakli matritsa deb atalasi.

Masalan, 2-matritsa to'g'ri burchakli matritsa.

$(a_{11} \ a_{12} \ a_{13})$ — satr matritsa,

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} \\ a_{12} \\ a_{13} \end{pmatrix} \text{ — ustun matritsa.}$$

Kvadrat matritsaning elementlaridan tuzilgan determinant matritsaning determinanti deyiladi.

Matritsani qisqacha bitta harf bilan belgilaymiz:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix}; \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

bu matritsalarining determinantlarini esa o`sha harflarni to`g`ri chiziqlar orasiga olamiz, ya`ni

$$|A| = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}; \quad |B| = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix}$$

Agar kvadrat matritsaning determinanti noldan farqli bo`lsa, u matritsa aynimagan, nolga teng bo`lsa, aynigan matritsa deyiladi.

Masalan, $A = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 6 \end{pmatrix}$; matritsa aynigan matritsa, chunki,

$$|A| = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 6 \end{vmatrix} = 12 - 12 = 0$$

$B = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 \end{pmatrix}$ — matritsa aynimagan, chunki,

$$|B| = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 \end{vmatrix} = 10 - 12 = -2 \neq 0$$

Matritsaning tengligi. Matritsalar ustida amallar.

Agar ikkita A va B matritsalarining satr va ustunlarini bir xil va mos elementlari o`zaro teng bo`lsa, u holda bu matritsalar o`zaro teng ($A=B$) matritsalar deyiladi:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{va} \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

matritsalar berilgan bo`lib, $a_{11} = b_{11}$, $a_{12} = b_{12}$, $a_{21} = b_{21}$, $a_{22} = b_{22}$ bo`lsa, $A=B$ bo`ladi.

Matritsalarini qo`shish.

Agar ikkita bir xil tartibli kvadrat matritsalar

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{va} \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

berilgan bo`lsa, u holda ularning yig`indisi

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} + b_{11} & a_{12} + b_{12} \\ a_{21} + b_{21} & a_{22} + b_{22} \end{pmatrix} \text{ bo`ladi.}$$

Agar bir xil tartibli to`g`ri burchakli matritsalar berilgan bo`lsa, ularning yig`indisi ham xuddi shuningdek aniqlanadi.

$$1\text{-misol. } \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 4 \\ 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 2 \\ 0 & 5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 3-1 & 4+2 \\ 1+0 & 2+5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 6 \\ 1 & 7 \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$2\text{-misol. } \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 1 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 5 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 3 \\ 2 & 4 & 6 \\ 3 & 2 & 5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 3 & 6 \\ 5 & 5 & 10 \\ 5 & 5 & 10 \end{pmatrix}$$

Matritsalarini qo`shish amali o`rin almashtirish va gruppalash qonunlari $A+B=B+A$, $(A+B)+C=A+(B+C)$ ga bo`ysunishini yengilgina isbotlash mumkin. Agar matritsaning hamma elementlari nollardan iborat bo`lsa, u nol-matritsa deb ataladi va (0) yoki 0 ko`rinishida yoziladi. Nol matritsani har qanday matritsaga qo`shganda yana o`sha matritsaning o`zi hosil bo`ladi.

$$\text{Masalan, } \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

Ikkinchi va uchinchi tartibli determinantlar.

Quyidagi: $\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}$ jadvalga ikkinchi tartibli determinant deyiladi. Bu yerda a_{11} , a_{12} , a_{21} , a_{22} uning elementlari, a_{11} , a_{12} –birinchi satr, a_{21} , a_{22} -ikkinchi satr, a_{11} , a_{21} - birinchi ustun, a_{12} , a_{22} ikkinchi ustun elementlari, a_{11} , a_{22} va a_{12} , a_{21} diagonal elementlari.

II-tartibli determinant ta`rifiga ko`ra asosan quyidagicha hisoblanadi:

$$\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix} = a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}a_{21} \quad (1)$$

va uni

$$\begin{vmatrix} \bullet & \bullet \\ \bullet & \bullet \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \bullet & \circ \\ \circ & \bullet \end{vmatrix} - \begin{vmatrix} \circ & \bullet \\ \bullet & \circ \end{vmatrix}$$

ko`rinishdagi sxemada tasvirlash mumkin.

III-tartibli determinant uchun unga mos formula

$$\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} = a_{11}a_{22}a_{33} + a_{12}a_{23}a_{31} + a_{13}a_{21}a_{32} - a_{13}a_{22}a_{31} - a_{12}a_{21}a_{33} - a_{11}a_{23}a_{32} \quad (2)$$

ko`rinishda bo`ladi. III-tartibli determinantni hisoblashda Sarrus (uchburchak) qoidasidan, ya`ni simvolik tarzda

qoidadan foydalanish mumkin

1-misol. Uchburchak qoidasidan foydalanib, quyidagi determinantni hisoblaymiz:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 & 3 & -2 \\ 2 & 0 & 3 \\ -2 & 1 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 1 \cdot 0 \cdot 2 + 3 \cdot 3 \cdot (-2) + 2 \cdot 2 \cdot (-2) - (-2) \cdot 0 \cdot (-2) - 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 - 1 \cdot 3 \cdot 1 = -37$$

1-Ta`rif. III-tartibli determinant biror elementining minori deb, u element turgan satr va ustunni o`chirishdan hosil bo`lgan ikkinchi tartibli determinantga aytiladi. Uni ikkita indeksli M bosh harf bilan belgilaymiz. Masalan a₁₁ elementga mos minor

$$M_{11} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} \text{ son bo`ladi.}$$

U III-tartibli determinantdan I-satr va I- ustunni o`chirishdan hosil bo`ladi.

2-Ta`rif. Determinant elementining algebraik to`ldiruvchisi deb, bu elementga mos va u turgan satr hamda ustun raqam yig`indisi juft bo`lganda musbat ishora bilan, bu yig`indi toq bo`lganda esa manfiy ishora bilan olingan minorga aytiladi.

a_{ij} elementning algebraik to`ldiruvchisi A_{ij} bilan belgilanadi, bu yerda i va j berilgan element turadigan satr va ustun raqami. Yuqoridagi ta`rifdan ko`rinadiki, elementning algebraik to`ldiruvchisi bilan uning minori orasidagi bog`lanish quyidagi

tenglik bilan ifodalanadi: $A_{ij} = (-1)^{i+j} M_{ij}$

Masalan:

$$A_{11} = (-1)^{1+1} M_{11} = M_{11}, A_{12} = (-1)^{1+2} M_{12} = -M_{12}$$

Yuqori tartibli determinantlarni hisoblashda ularning tartibini pasaytirish qoidasidan foydalanish mumkin. Bu qoida determinantni biror satr yoki ustun elementlarining algebraik to`ldiruvchilari bo`yicha yoyish mumkinligiga asoslangan.

Masalan, (2) determinantni birinchi satr elementlarining algebraik to`ldiruvchilari bo`yicha quyidagicha yoyish mumkin:

$$\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} = a_{11} \begin{vmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} - a_{12} \begin{vmatrix} a_{21} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} + a_{13} \begin{vmatrix} a_{21} & a_{22} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} \end{vmatrix}$$

Determinantning quyidagi xossalarini keltiramiz:

Agar determinant satrlari elementlari o`rnini ularga mos ustun elementlari bilan almashtirsa, uning qiymati o`zgarmaydi.

Agar satr yoki ustun elementlarining o`rni almashtirilganda, determinantning ishorasi qarama-qarshisiga o`zgaradi.

Ikki bir xil satrli (yoki ustunli) determinant qiymati nolga teng.

Satrdagi (yoki ustundagi) umumiy ko`paytuvchini determinant belgisidan tashqariga chiqarib yozish mumkin.

Agar biror satr (yoki ustun) ning barcha elementlari nolga teng bo`lsa, u holda determinantning qiymati nolga teng.

Agar determinantning biror satri (yoki ustuni) elementlariga boshqa satr (yoki ustun) ning bir xil songa ko`paytirilgan mos elementlari qo`shilsa, determinant o`z qiymatini o`zgartirmaydi.

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